

ISic1348

I.Sicily inscription 1348

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 303

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [] Αλύρήλι
2. [ο]ς Ῥεστοῦτος
3. καὶ Ζωσίμη
4. ἡγοράσομεν
5. [έ]κ τῶν ἰδγείων
6. [ήμῃ]ν ἐνβασιν

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Aurelios Restoutos and Zosime, built this sepulchre/sarcophagus at their own expense.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492957

EDCS 39101722

PHI 140846

PHI 140847

PHI 140848

PHI 316258

Bibliography

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